

Research Libraries, Researchers & the EOSC: Multidisciplinary Universities

*Workshop Report. Written by Ignasi
Labastida*

General Notes

LIBER, the Association of European Research Libraries, and Scientific Knowledge Services have organised a series of workshops on the interaction between research libraries, researchers, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) during the last two weeks of January. These workshops were aimed at discussing the role of the libraries in connecting researchers to Open Science and the EOSC, and at analysing how their services developed to support researchers can be integrated into the EOSC.

The series consisted of five workshops, three of them focused on different European regions, and two of them dedicated to multidisciplinary and technical universities, respectively.

On the 25th of January the fourth workshop of the series was held virtually. This fourth workshop was dedicated to multidisciplinary universities. Beside presenters, moderator and organisers there were around 30 participants from a dozen of European countries, mainly north western.

The workshop began with an introductory presentation from the moderator, Bertil Dorch, Library Director at the University Library of Southern Denmark, who set up the main goal of the workshop: to discuss on the Interaction Between Research Libraries, Researchers, and the EOSC.

The event was organised in three parts:

- The first one dedicated to listening to three panelists that presented different experiences.

- The second one focused on the actual discussion in three different virtual rooms.
- The third one aimed at exchanging the results of the separate discussions in a plenary room.

Presentations

The first speaker was **Paul Ayris**, pro-vice-provost at University College of London who presented what research universities need from EOSC. Ideally he asked for a place to have everything with a complete coverage of all subject disciplines and provided as a Google-like catalogue with high relevance results. He mentioned the LERU roadmap on Open Science and its new implementation report where EOSC is analysed along with research data and legal aspects. Those two documents include recommendations to universities like developing the Dutch model of Data stewardship and undertaking a study on the use of Open Data by universities and industries. Furthermore he shared the call for a European Digital University Act made by professor Karen Max, rector of the University of Amsterdam a few weeks ago. This act could help to overcome the concerns about having too many commercial partnerships between universities and industry in research. With research data, universities cannot repeat the mistakes they made with publications. They cannot hand over rights to commercial parties when it could be better to retain them.

Finally, he stressed the need to begin a cultural change in research institutions to deliver FAIR research data and involve researchers in the EOSC. This change must be a process not a single event. It is actually a big challenge and we cannot repeat the mistake done during the Ebola crisis where 65% of the data was not shared or made available. The partnership among universities and EOSC must go beyond the aggregation of metadata if we want to meet this challenge of delivering reusable research data.

"Let EOSC be more than just an aggregator"

Figure 1: Let EOSC be more than just an aggregator (Denkschets, 2021)

He concluded by asking EOSC to not just be an aggregator but to bring real partnerships, to show leadership in research data management and to provide co-creation solutions to universities. If EOSC does not play this role now, it will fail because universities are already shaping the development of new Open Science solutions.

Paul Ayris was followed by **Susana Nykyri**, manager of Open Science services at Tampere University. She shared the case of her university and her country, Finland, and her experience as a member of the EOSC Landscape Working Group. This group had the task to map the existing research infrastructures in Europe which are candidates to be part of the EOSC federation. This mapping included the detection of the readiness of the infrastructures in being part of EOSC.

The mapping was not easy because there was not a formal definition of EOSC readiness and a clear definition of infrastructure. Nevertheless the group analysed the existence of policies and infrastructures at country level. The existence of an Open Science policy or a portal with a list of infrastructures helped in performing the analysis. This is the case of Finland that was identified as one of the countries with a higher level of readiness along with the Netherlands and Norway.

The working group identified the need of more actions on data management and the development of competences in scientific computing and other research services. Nykiri shared some of the solutions available in Finland like the creation of data services provided by national organisations, the existence of expert panels and working groups and how policies are monitored.

Finally she shared the case of Tampere University, a new university born in 2019 from the merger of former universities of the city. Its library has included a new area of services for Open Science along with Information Resources and Learning Services. Although the library plays an important role, Open Science is everybody's business. For that reason the university has established an Open Science working group. From her experience she recommended the development of a service of data stewardship and to show the costs and the consequences of not developing a good data management

The first part of the event ended with the third speaker, **Sylvia Koukounidou**, coordinator of the Digitization and Archives Office of the University of Cyprus Library. She talked about how ready libraries are to support EOSC. She shared the results of a survey conducted within the NI4OS project. In this survey, all relevant stakeholders in EOSC were asked how familiar they were with EOSC. The results show that researchers are a bit familiar but they need further training. In the same survey, participants were asked in which areas they need training in relation to data management. The answers suggest that this training can be handled by libraries. Libraries are expected to play a relevant role in policy making, data curation, data stewardship, data science, data analysis and education. In fact, how different is the scope of EOSC from a library scope?

What research libraries need from EOSC

Figure 2: What research libraries need from EOSC (Denkschets, 2021)

Libraries can be seen as a multidisciplinary one stop-shop to support researchers in open science, as open content providers, as educators and an important asset to policy makers for the creation, implementation and monitoring of policies. Libraries seem to be ready to play these roles because they have experience in well established networks and they are well connected and organised. Moreover they have a lot of knowledge gained through the years in different open science issues. However there are a lot of challenges, especially in costs and funding. There is a lack of resources in staff and infrastructures, there is a need to allocate dedicated positions on open science in the libraries and there is also a lot of training needed. Maybe library schools need to include already in their curricula some of the aspects of open science services.

Sylvia ended her talk with two questions to discuss further with the participants. Are libraries really ready? How can make EOSC a success by prioritising the needs of libraries?

Highlights (breakout rooms and the research questions)

After the three presentations, participants were split in three breakout rooms (square, oval and triangle rooms) to discuss and answer four questions:

- What is the value of EOSC for researchers and research libraries, based on the goals/work of the EOSC?
- What is the input needed from these stakeholders towards of the EOSC
- How can these stakeholders groups be actively involved in EOSC activities and what do they need to get involved?
- What feedback mechanism could be built to continuously inform EOSC, in its quest to remain an agile infrastructure

The discussions in the breakout rooms were facilitated by the three speakers that chose among the participants a volunteer to report back to the plenary at the end. Each breakout had around five or six participants apart from the speakers and organisers. The discussion was mainly focused on answering the four questions available in the corresponding jamboards. There were not any initial comments on what it was said previously in the three presentations. Most of the participants were not familiar with jamboards. Initially it was not clear how they could participate and add notes and they used the microphone to give their opinions. Generally the contributions were added in the board and commented but there was a lack of time to wrap up them and to set a final common position for each question. This task was supposedly left to the participant who had to report back later in the plenary. It must be said that not all speakers had the skill to facilitate the discussion. Probably in next workshops it would be advisable to use facilitators instead of the speakers who can also contribute in the discussion as any other participant. In some groups there were a couple of active participants while the rest remained silent and only participated by adding notes on the board without giving any opinion.

Regarding the questions, sometimes there were terms that were not clear for all participants. Not everyone was familiar with the goals of EOSC or which stakeholders were discussed in the conversation.

After the three separate discussions ended, the results were shared in the plenary.

Here there is a summary of what it was said:

EOSC is seen as a joint infrastructure and a one-stop-shop for services. It is also seen as a possible means for disseminating training materials it could lay the foundation for service level agreements.

EOSC can potentially create interoperability of metadata, it can unify guidance for research data management and it can help build local initiatives and make repositories compatible. However now there is a need to have more guidance on how to be engaged and how to participate

Besides being a single point of access, EOSC is also expected to be a main multidisciplinary and multi-country resource for researchers and libraries. It is important to remark that EOSC needs to keep a balance among all sciences and not prioritise just some.

In a positive way, EOSC can be cost-efficient for libraries for sharing training resources, documentation and tools. The need of meeting EOSC requirements and expectations could help research institutions to make some development work in terms of what they are able to offer

There is a need to have an agreement about policies, standards, definitions responsibilities in each institution. Research institutions need to have a link to EOSC to provide internal leadership and they also have to commit to performing training on data management. This training needs to be done at all levels of the institution and begin with training the trainers. However there is a feeling that the benefits of being part of EOSC are still not clear. There is a lack of guidance on how to participate in the association and why. The membership has a fee but there has not been a cost analysis of the interaction with EOSC

Libraries can build the trust needed among EOSC and the researchers. They can also promote EOSC services as the first choice but there is a need to have a compelling case to sell. EOSC can be competing with other solutions that could be seen more immediately and closer for researchers. Libraries can be the intermediaries between EOSC and institutions and they can also gather feedback from researchers and communicate it to association. Although now it is not easy to access EOSC, libraries can communicate to users how to use EOSC effectively and also report back the feedback from the user experience. Moreover libraries can ensure that researchers and decision makers in institutions are aware of EOSC and its activities.

In relation to ways of getting involved in EOSC activities, participants asked for more dialogue among universities and the EOSC. It is clear that EOSC is a small association with not a large budget in comparison of the number of existing universities in Europe. This difficulty in scaling the communication in both ways can be overcome by using existing membership organisations like LIBER, LERU or the EUA. Another suggestion made was to form focus groups or working groups with the participation of librarians and researchers. Communication can also be achieved by establishing national nodes that can provide feedback from countries and can allow small organisations to have their voice in EOSC. The association needs to receive feedback not only from librarians, researchers' opinions are essential. A mechanism for feedback could be an annual survey. Finally, EOSC could establish some awards and acknowledge best practices in a way to get more engagement.

Conclusions

As a conclusion of the workshop it can be said that EOSC is expected to be a useful infrastructure to share and provide high quality research data but there is still not clear how to participate, how to be engaged and which are the benefits for research institutions to join the association.

Libraries are willing to become the intermediaries among EOSC and researchers as they have been in other similar situations. They are ready to play this role although they acknowledge that they have to get more training and they need to make internal changes to deliver the expected service.

Finally, universities want to be heard and to play a more relevant role in the development of EOSC. They feel that the association has been created without hearing them but they want to build new channels of communication.

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